

An Interface of Classroom Examination Practices and the Success for Licensure Examination for Teachers

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ABSTRACT

To be of significance to nation building, a prospective teacher needs to pass the licensure examination for teachers, as prescribed by law under the “Philippine Professionalization Act of 1994.” In line with this, the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology is undertaking efforts in delivering quality education by requiring its faculty to comply with the highest standards of educational qualification as it recognizes the role of teachers in facilitating students’ learning.

A self-constructed questionnaire was used to gather data consisting of open-ended question form enquiring how students prepare themselves for the examinations and the practices of the teachers before, during and after the examinations. To clarify answers not clearly stated, interviews were conducted. The 68 third year Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) for the SY 2018-2019 were chosen as respondents. Data gathered were analysed using the thematic analysis approach.

Findings show that the respondents prepare themselves spiritually, physically and mentally for the examinations. Teachers make necessary class preparations before the examinations except those who included items in the test not covered in class, which may affect students’ test attitudes ultimately result to unfavorable performance in the LET.

It is recommended that teachers create test questions that follow the LET format so that students become familiar with the setup. This may also develop the students’ test-taking skills while studying to ensure better performance in the LET.

Keywords: Prospective teachers, licensure examinations, students’ engagement.

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INTRODUCTION

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) offering teacher education program like the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology (ASIST) carry a challenging role in developing globally competent and effective prospective teachers with employable skills and good attitudes ready to compete in the global market (Aquino, 2015). Students in the province of Abra aspiring to enrol teacher education consider ASIST as their top priority school. This is supported by the pattern of exponential increase in population of students interested to enrol in the teacher education as shown in the application in the admission examination of the college.

One reason for this is its low tuition fee as ASIST is the only State College and University (SUC) in the province of Abra catering to the needs of marginalized population who aims to improve their lives through education.

As a Teacher Education Institution (HEI), its main role is to provide quality pre-service training to prospective teachers in coordination with the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in accordance with the pertinent provisions of the Republic Act (RA) No. 7722 otherwise known as the “Higher Education Act of 1994”, for the purpose of streamlining the undergraduate teacher education in the country to keep step on the demands of global competitiveness (Escarlos, 2017). In short, TEIs are assigned the function and responsibility in the preparation and training of prospective teachers.

In line with this, the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology is undertaking efforts in delivering quality education as it envisions to be “a university that produces graduates who are academically competitive, locally responsive and globally sustained.” To ensure this, it requires its faculty to observe and comply with the highest standards of educational qualification in their own field of specialization. In addition, it also supports the attendance of faculty in relevant trainings and seminars, and within its financial capability, allots for the improvement of infra-structure including ICT. This is so because ASIST recognizes the role of quality teachers in facilitating students’ learning thereby becoming useful citizens in nation building and economic development.

Background

To be of significance to nation building, a prospective teacher needs to pass the Licensure Examination for Teachers, as prescribed by the Professional Regulatory Commission (PRC) tasked to strengthen the supervision and regulation of the teaching profession in the Philippines prescribed by law under Republic Act (RA) No. 7836 known as the Philippine Professionalization Act of 1994. This Act is put into law to strengthen the regulation and supervision of the practice of teaching in the Philippines and prescribing a Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) and for other purposes, which became a law in December 16, 1994.

Article IV of Section 27 of the said Act requires that, except otherwise allowed under this Act, no person shall practice or offer to practice the teaching profession in the Philippines be appointed as teacher to any position calling for a teacher position without having previously obtained a valid certificate of registration and a valid professional license from the Commission. As herein stipulated, to be registered means to have valid professional license, hence, a prospective teacher is required to pass the LET. It is assumed that LET is a good measure of competencies needed for effective teaching acquired in school. These competencies are reflected in the National Competency-Based Standards (NCBTS) now the Philippine

Professional Standard for Teachers (PPST). LET result distinguishes those who are capable to enter into teaching profession and those who are not, hence, the supply of teachers is ideally limited to those who are competent.

In its mission to produce employable graduates of the teacher education, ASIST has gone a long way in improving the performance of graduates in the LET having done the aforementioned steps. Despite all these actions, results of the licensure examinations did not improve. Thus, there must be a gap somewhere why students perform fairly in the Licensure Examinations for Teachers for over the years now.

In their fullest capacity, the TEIs including ASIST have been holding in time the responsibility in producing potential and quality graduates. However, past and current trends show that the low passing rate of those taking the LET has not improved. In 2016, LET result officially released on November 28, 2016 by the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) and the Board of Professional Teachers (BPT), only 23,378 out of 77,466 examinees (30.18%) passed the exam for the elementary education level and only 31,334 out of 92,754 examinees (33.78%) were successful in the secondary education level country wide. In ASIST – Bangued, the LET performance in September 2016 for elementary education is lower than the national passing rate. Institutional passing rate was 25% while the national passing rate was 30.18%. For the secondary education, the institutional passing rate was far below than the national passing rate. The institutional passing rate was 12.99% while the national passing rate was 33.78%. In May 2017, result of the LET performance of ASIST Bangued Campus where this study is conducted, is lower than the national passing rate. For elementary education, the institutional passing rate was 7.34% compared to the national passing rate of 10.39%. For secondary education, the institutional passing rate was 18.92% compared to the national passing rate of 25.46%. This is the most recent result during the time this study is conducted.

Several studies were undertaken to look into account factors that affect students' performance in the LET. Student-related as well as faculty-related factors were investigated. As to student-related factors, it was found out that the following are linked to better result in the Licensure Examination for Teachers: attendance to LET review (Aquino, 2015), the field study courses and internship training (Kalaw, 2017), area of specialization (Pacheco, 2017), profile of examinees (Figuerras, 2013), academic achievement (Rabanal, 2016), the college admission scores (Ferrer, 2017), English proficiency (Hena, 2017), and, GPA of students (Soriano, 2017). More importantly, the teachers' competence was found to be significantly related to the successful examination result among the takers.

The aforementioned student-related factors therefore projects that student engagement is necessary in the attainment of one's goals. A teacher education graduate's prime goal after graduation is to pass the licensure examination. HEIs on the other hand are focusing their attention on the role of faculty as designers of educational environments to support engagement

(Faltado, 2017), especially that there is fluctuating trends of academic outcomes particularly in the results of licensure examinations.

In so far as student engagement is concerned, a stimuli-response (S-R) is considered here. When teachers give stimulus, a corresponding response from the students is expected. This is the argument in this study, to determine the practices of teachers before, during and after examinations which are considered as stimuli to a meaningful student engagement, ultimately prepares them to successful examination result.

It is in this premise that this study is conducted to look into factors influential to a favourable examination. To attain this goal, this study aims to benchmark an interface between classroom examination practices and the success for Licensure Examination for Teachers. It is disputed in here, that when students are attuned to a good examination practice and environment while in school, it is most likely that in taking the Licensure Examination for Teachers, they are already conditioned to that background. Specifically, it aims to i) determine what activities are commonly done by the CTE students in preparation for examinations, during examinations and after examinations; ii) identify practices of teachers as perceived by the students before examinations, during examinations and after examinations; and, iii) generate list of expectations from the teachers and administration perceived by the students as helpful tool to improve students' engagement and ultimately to successful examination results.

The contribution of this study would be of interest to the college as its result would be used as baseline information for the improvement of instruction and policy formulation resulting in improved result in the graduates' performance in the LET. This study may challenge the faculty to improve logistics of conducting the examinations and to look for strategies helpful in enhancing the performance of students in the classroom and ultimately in the licensure examinations. Moreover, the result of this study may inspire the administration to allot commendable fund in support to the realization of a more promising learning environment.

Objective

This study aims to determine an interface of classroom examination practices and success for licensure examination for teachers. Specifically, it aims to i) determine what activities are commonly done by the College of Teacher Education students in preparation for examinations, during examinations and after the examinations; ii) identify practices of teachers as perceived by the students before examinations, during examinations and after examinations; and, generate list of expectations from the teachers and administration perceived by the students as helpful tools to increase students' engagement and ultimately towards successful examinations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Background Theory

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Previous Studies

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The aforementioned student-related factors therefore projects that student engagement is necessary in the attainment of one's goals. A teacher education graduate's prime goal after graduation is to pass the licensure examination. HEIs on the other hand are focusing their attention on the role of faculty as designers of educational environments to support engagement (Faltado, 2017), especially that there is fluctuating trends of academic outcomes particularly in the results of licensure examinations.

METHODOLOGY

Data

Data gathered were the responses of the respondents on real-life situations describing their experiences and views on taking an exam, and in any form they were most comfortable with. Answers were expressed in Ilocano, the widely used vernacular in the province, in English or in Filipino, the national language. Answers of respondents were in bullet form, in a sentence, or in paragraph. They stated how they prepare themselves for examinations, what they do during and after examinations. They also gave impressions on what their teachers do in preparing the respondents for the exam, what they do during and after the exam. Furthermore, they also expressed their expectations from their teachers and the department per se which they think is helpful to them in having a better test result.

Data gathered was analyzed using the thematic analysis approach. Semantically similar words, phrases and/or sentences that forms meaningful units from responses were grouped together accordingly, and were further categorized into higher-order level of the subject.

Method

This study used descriptive method of research, as it describes the activities and practices commonly done by the students and teachers before the examinations, during the examinations and after the examinations. Likewise, it describes the perceptions of students from teachers and administration perceived as helpful in improving engagement of students and ultimately to successful result in the Licensure Examination of Teachers. Responses of students during the interviews were qualitatively considered.

A self-constructed questionnaire was used to gather data. It consists of open-ended question form where participants would answer as many as classroom real-life situations describing their experiences and views on taking an exam, and in any form they are most comfortable with. They may answer in Ilocano, English or in Filipino; in bullet form, in a sentence, or in paragraph. They were asked how they prepare themselves for examinations, what they do during and after examinations. They were also asked what their teachers do in preparing them for the exam, what they do during and after the exam. Furthermore, they were asked what they expect from teachers and the department per se which they think is helpful to them in having a better test result.

The tool was validated by three faculty from the teacher education department and was pilot tested with the (Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) generalist, Bachelor of Elementary Education major in Pre-school Education (PSEd) and Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education (BTTE) third year students in the same department.

To clarify answers not clearly stated, interviews were conducted.

Third year BSEd students for the SY 2018-2019 were chosen as respondents as they are expectedly more mature, have longer classroom interaction and wider perception with their teachers, more test-taking experiences, as compared with those students in the lower year level. There are 68 of them. Purposive sampling was employed.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Results

The data gathered and analyzed are presented and discussed in the subsequent section. Responses gathered were coded, grouped accordingly by a common denominator and further categorized into higher-order level of the topic.

On Students' Activities in Preparation for the Examinations

The questions asked in the first part of the questionnaire were the things that the respondents do in preparation for the exam, during exam and after the exam. For what they do in preparation for the exams, the respondents listed 41 responses and these are presented in Table 1a that follows.

Table 1a. Students' Activities in Preparation for Exams

What Students Do Before Examinations			
Self-Conditioning Activities	A. Spiritual		16
	• praying		
	B. Physical		37
	• eating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ peanuts ○ any food ○ sweets ○ chocolates 	
	• resting		12
	• sleeping		16
	• relaxing		67
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ connecting with friends/family thru the social media ○ watching TV/movie ○ attending a family bonding ○ hanging out with friends ○ playing gadgets ○ strolling ○ listening to music 	
	• exercising		2
	C. Emotional		11
	• to be confident		
	• to be hopeful		
	❖ nervous		
	❖ confused		
Test Conditioning Activities	• Review Style	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Thorough Review ○ Memorizing/recalling ○ Scanning notes 	55
	• Review Preparation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Make a reviewer/review note ○ Completing notes ○ Copy notes from classmates ○ Borrowing books ○ Read related topics from the net ○ Solicit help from classmates/friends <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Scope of the test ❖ Schedule of the test 	77
	• Review Techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Review with a partner ○ Review while watching TV ○ Review while eating ○ Reading aloud ○ Reading aloud while recording ○ Jotting down new words while reading 	22

Struggles Before Examinations	A. Home-Related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Doing household chores ○ Engaging into livelihood 	21
	B. Teacher-Related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Finishing project/requirements ○ Finishing assignment ○ Finishing report/IMs 	48
	C. Personal-Related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Secure clearance/permit ○ Settlement of financial obligations/fines ○ Prepare personal things needed for the exams 	12

Students' Activities in Preparation for Exams

The table shows that as preparation for the exams, the respondents perform self-conditioning activities categorized as spiritual, physical, and emotional. On spiritual aspect, even though the respondents are studying in a public school, they have high regard for spirituality as a way to condition themselves. They believe in the power of a prime mover – God. Moreover, on the physical aspect, they engage themselves in relaxing activities by connecting with friends/relatives through the social media before the exams, and this has garnered the highest frequency. In addition, they also mentioned that sleeping is a way to help them prepare physically for the exam. In terms of self-conditioning activities, the respondents claim to have thoroughly reviewed and read related topics from the internet. They review their notes as they need to complete them before review time through borrowing notes from classmates or from borrowed books. They stated that they are more confident when they make a reviewer which indicates that the respondents are visual learners in nature. Many of them find confidence in reviewing with a partner, one who asks a question and the other to answer and vice versa.

The table further shows the struggles they go through prior to the exams, which may affect their preparation. Most of them are tied up finishing requirements and assignments taking most of their time, instead of reviewing. Many claim they do household chores whereas others are engaged in livelihood. This is substantial evidence that many among the respondents are working for themselves and for their school expenses and this may somehow impact their preparation for exams. Personal-related circumstances are minimal.

It is evident that during the preparation of the exams, the respondents display a moderately high level of engagement in reviewing as well as complying with requirements, assignments and reports as shown by the 48 of those who claim they are doing it. As for them, they cannot focus reviewing while thinking of unfinished undertaking, like their projects, assignments, and reports as mentioned by the respondents during the interview. *“Diak maka concentrate agreview Ma’am no adu ti panpanunutek nga requirements nga diak pay nalpas, isu nga ileppas ko pay nga umuna saak to agreview.”* (I cannot focus reviewing when there are unfinished projects and other requirements to be submitted left undone. I need to accomplish it first then sit down and review). This means that students find importance, as a part of their learning and academic obligations to comply with what the teachers require them, as a part of their academic achievement. Their amenability to such activities like making projects, assignments and reports is a display of acquired skills and competencies needed to do

such. It is an accepted dictum that one cannot give what one does not have, in the same manner as one cannot teach what one does not know (Ferrer, et al, 2015). In application, if they do not have the skills and competencies, they avoid doing such. In short, the respondents are engaged in preparing themselves in the profession, yet, they are faced with various tasks that may challenge them at this point.

On Students' Activities During Examinations

When asked about what the respondents do during examinations, they listed 27 items which were further analyzed and grouped accordingly. These responses are presented in Table 1b below.

Table 1b. Students' Activities During Exams

Students' Activities During Exams		
Self-Conditioning Techniques	A. Spiritual	17
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Praying • Attending early mass before going to school 	
	B. Physical	13
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eating before going to the test • Relax and prepare for exam • Wake up early 	
Test Taking Techniques	C. Emotional	8
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I tell myself I can do it • I keep myself calm • I tell myself that test is a part of student's journey 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Negative Emotions Felt ✚ Afraid of not passing the test ✚ Feeling nervous ✚ Feeling pressured 	9
	D. Mental	24
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scanning notes in between exam period • Cramming review in between exam period 	
Test Taking Techniques	A. Before Answering	9
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyze questions • Read directions carefully • Listen to directions given by the teacher • Browse test questions/test paper 	
	B. While Answering	28
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I recall reviewed topics • I keep focused • Answer questions which I am more comfortable with • I leave difficult items • If I can't understand the question, I ask my classmate 	
	C. After Answering	11
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good Practice ✓ I go back to difficult items 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ I go over my paper ✓ I review my answers • Bad Practice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ I ask friends answer of unanswered items ✓ I peep at answers of classmates 	9
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Students' Activities During Exams

The table shows that respondents perform four types of self-conditioning activities during the exams namely spiritual, physical, emotional, and mental. Among these four categories, spiritual and mental activities are highest among responses with 17 and 15 each respectively. On the day of the exam, they pray and scan their notes when they have the opportunity. They feel more confident when they scan their notes before the teacher arrives in the classroom. While waiting for the teacher to distribute the test papers, many of them are cramming. On the physical aspect, they also wake up early and eat breakfast before going to the testing center. Emotionally, some of them are also nervous and pressured while others try to calm themselves and to settle their feelings before they start the examinations. These feelings indicate that examinations matters much in a student's endeavors. Examination is a big thing which forms part of their achievement. Some feel afraid of not passing it. As a respondent claim during the interview, "*kasapulan nga makaruarak iti test ko Ma'am tapno awan to mabati nga subject ko nga iraprapin kon no sumaruno nga semester*". (I need to pass all my exams Ma'am so I will not have additional subjects to enrol in the next semester). Another claims "*Ikarigatak iti makaruar kadagiti amin nga exam ko ita Ma'am, ta no ma fail nak iti maysa a subject, saan nak ton a maawat ditoy teacher education inton sumaruno nga semester.*" (I need to pass all my examinations Ma'am because when I fail even in one subject, I may no longer be admitted in the teacher education next semester).

Only two responses were recorded for reading directions before answering the exams. This may be due to some taker's emotional instability, as they feel pressured when faced with examinations. Further, only a few claim that good testing techniques are – to leave difficult items by first answering questions they are more comfortable with, by going over the test questions, and by reviewing their answers. Most of them may not have been aware of these helpful techniques; hence, when they will take the LET, they will practice taking the LET the way they are used to in the classroom. These good test-taking practices should be given attention immediately, so that prior to taking the LET, the respondents still have time to exercise these helpful test techniques until they are used to.

On Students' Activities After the Examinations

When asked about what they do after the examinations, the respondents listed 31 answers which were further coded and analyzed and is presented in Table 1c.

Table 1c. Students' Activities After Exams

Students' Activities After Exams		
A. Learning-Gains Oriented Practices	• I review my mistakes	14
	• I look for the answer of a difficult item	12
	• I promise myself to do better next time	8
	• I and my classmates discuss items in the test	3

B. Score-Oriented Practices	• I check on my score	28
	• I recount the number of checks and tallies with the written score	18
	• I compare score of my classmates with my score	7
	• I count the number of items with wrong answers	6
C. Recognition-Oriented Practices	• I tell my friends of my high score in the test	11
	• I feel so proud of getting high score in the test	10
	• I show my score/paper to my parents	8
	• I keep my paper	2
D. Others	• I feel relaxed because test is over	10
	• I thank God for my good performance	8

After taking the examinations, the respondents employ various three types of practices pertaining to learning goals, scores, and recognition. The table reveals that among the three practices, it is the score-oriented practices which stand out. In particular, looking at scores immediately tops the list with 28 counts, followed by the recounting the number of correct items and tallying it with the written scores. This is a very frequent observation in the classroom. Only few students look at items marked with x and immediately look for the correct answer, before tallying the number of items marked with check with their written scores.

In addition, there are also respondents who claim that they review their mistakes at 14 counts and look for answer of a difficult item, either from their notes, from their teacher or from a classmate at 12 counts. Moreover, some respondents indicate they are happy having a good performance as revealed by the test result. Some tell their friends about it, while others show their papers to their parents.

On Teachers' Activities in Preparing Students for Exams

When students were asked of their teachers' practices and activities before, during and after examinations, they disclose both favorable and unfavorable ones.

The respondents listed responses as activities of their teachers in preparing them for the exams which were further coded, grouped and presented in Table 2a.

Table 2a. Teachers' Activities in Preparing Students for Exams

Teachers' Activities in Preparing Students for Exams		
A. Preparatory Motives	• Give coverage of the test	28
	• Conduct short class review	28
	• Remind class to review very well	16
	• Wrap-up topics tackled	13
	• Give instructions (Seating arrangement, permits, etc)	13
	• Remind the class of test schedule	7
	• Tell the class of the examination type	4

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remind the class to settle school obligations (eg permit) 	4
B. Independent Learning Motives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Give the last meeting before the exams for students to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Review ✓ Finish requirements/ Projects ✓ Study unfinished topics included in the test 	18 15 12
C. Assessment of Output Motives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collect requirement/projects Give requirement/project for instantaneous submission 	14 11
D. Reinforcement Motives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Give reward to students with excellent performance in the test Boosts confidence of students 	3 3
E. Personal Motives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does not meet class last meeting before exams to prepare test questions 	4

The table discloses common practices of teachers in preparing students for examinations. As to preparatory activities, teachers give the coverage of the test and conduct short class review at 28 counts each. The teachers also remind students to review and settle obligations, and instruct them on what are needed during examinations. Apart from that, teachers also allow for independent learning practices by making the last class session before the exam as an opportunity for students to review (18) and to finish requirements (15).

On Teachers' Activities During Exams

When asked about what the teachers do on the day of examinations, the respondents listed the following as shown in Table 2b below.

Table 2b. Teachers' Activities During Exams

A. Test Preparatory Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> address common problems on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ seating arrangement ✓ collection of test paper payment ✓ personal necessities of students ✓ examination permits ✓ proper placement of review materials and other personal belongings reminds students <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ not to cheat ✓ to follow directions given in the test ✓ to be conscious of time limit 	44 32
B. Test Facilitating Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> make corrections on typographically erroneous items ask students what is not clear to them 	8

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> answer questions of students 	
C. Test Monitoring Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Roam around the classroom to monitor individual progress of students ✓ Sit in front while observing individual students ✓ Check who are cheating ✓ Sit in front and do paper works 	29
D. Test Motivating Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wishing students “Good Luck” Promise of reward to a student with a perfect score 	7

It is revealed that before conducting the exams, teachers address administrative matters in the classroom like seating arrangement, cheating, following directions, and collecting test paper payment among others. In terms of reliable test results, teachers monitor student’s individual progress and sit in front while invigilating. On the other hand, the respondents listed practices of their teachers which undoubtedly yield a less reliable test result.

On Expectation of Students from Teachers During Examinations

The table below shows the listed expectations of students from their teachers during examinations.

Table 3. Expectations of Students from Teachers During Examinations

Expectations of Students from Teachers During Examinations		
A. On Test Items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Avoid giving items in the test not covered in class Ask students what part of the test is difficult Give time to discuss in class unfamiliar/difficult items with corresponding answer 	8 5 5
B. On test result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Give immediate feedback on the result of the test Give due recognition to students who performed well in the test Conduct conference with students who performed fairly in the test <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ for encouragement ✓ for diagnosis of difficulties/need 	18 12 4 3
C. On Classroom Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impose: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ discipline especially during examinations ✓ disciplinary action to students caught cheating ✓ strict compliance of students on deadlines of requirements 	8 5 3
D. On teacher duties and responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Towards students <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ attend classes religiously ✓ be more passionate to teach ✓ give ample time for students in making requirements/projects ✓ check test papers personally Towards the school 	9 8 8 5 5

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ make grades available at the Registrar's Office on-time for students' quick compliance on scholarship requirements ✓ design a more conducive seating arrangement during examination period to protect the integrity of the test result 	4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • others <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ give a rest day after the exams 	3

Table 3 reveals expectations of students from their teachers in terms of test items, test results, classroom policies, and teacher's duties and responsibilities during examinations. On test items, the respondents expect their teachers not to give items not covered in class with 8 counts.

This means that most students are not yet engaged in independent learning. They want verbatim from the textbook to be seen in the test. Secondly on test results, the respondents expect their teachers to give immediate feedback on the result of the test as claimed by 18 respondents. This enables students to review items that were not answered correctly, and for students to know how well they performed in the test, and to what extent they would strive for the better. In addition, they expect their teachers to recognize those who do well in the test as claimed by 12 respondents. On the other hand, some students hate cheating as shown in the table as they expect their teachers to strictly enforce discipline during tests and give disciplinary action to monitor students caught cheating in the test.

In terms of teachers' duties and responsibilities during examinations, the respondents oftentimes observe that some faculty members do not regularly and religiously attend their classes. While students are scolded or reprimanded in coming to school late, many of their teachers do not religiously attend classes, they further claim. As one respondent said, "*dapat koma met Ma'am, always present teachers. No dakami ti maladaw wenno agabsent, mauntan kami*". (Teachers should also come to school religiously as we do. When students come late or absent, we are being reprimanded). This means that classroom interaction is very important to them. They still look upon the teachers as the best facilitator of learning.

The students also claim in their expectations that all teachers should submit the grades on time to the Registrar's Office for a ready reference on grade requirement for scholarship purposes. There are also respondents claiming for a rest day after examination to tone down their stress during their preparation for the examination. This suggests that examinations be given on the middle of the week towards weekend for students to rest them to rest on the weekend.

On Expectations of Students from the Department During Examinations

When asked about the expectations of students from the department, the respondents listed and shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Expectation of Students from the Department During Examinations

Expectation of Students from the Department During Examinations				
A. On Examinations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test Schedule <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ There should be definite test schedule ✓ Definite schedule of exams posted in advance ✓ Teachers to strictly follow posted schedule of examinations ✓ Conduct of lectures/classes should be avoided during examination schedule • Test Room Environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Test rooms should be sustained with quiet corridors ✓ Unused classrooms should be kept closed to prevent students from loitering • Test Validity and Integrity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Strict observance of teachers on seating arrangement at all times ✓ Strict implementation of school policies to students caught cheating ✓ Use of bluebooks/green books by all teachers ✓ Regulated format, content and payment of test papers 	<p>12</p> <p>12</p> <p>10</p> <p>9</p> <p>9</p> <p>5</p> <p>8</p> <p>5</p> <p>4</p> <p>4</p>		
	B. On Students' Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • more and updated books in the library • more and updated technologies used in the classroom • convenient students' lounge • well-lighted and well-ventilated classrooms • opportunities for academic competitions • less extra-curricular activities, more classroom interaction • free from cleaning rooms and other errands during examinations day • result of exams and over-all performance be posted in strategic places • regulated type and deadline of requirements/projects 	<p>6</p> <p>6</p> <p>5</p> <p>4</p> <p>4</p> <p>4</p> <p>4</p> <p>4</p> <p>3</p>	
		3. Other Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • monitoring of teachers' regular attendance in classes 	<p>6</p>

Table 4 shows responses of students when asked about their expectations from their department. These expectations as claimed by the respondents bear importance in the attainment of better result of examinations and in their academic performance as a whole and ultimately in the performance in the LET. They claim of a definite test schedule to be posted earlier and to be strictly followed by the teachers. When this is strictly implemented, it will unburden the students of rushing in taking the test under one teacher while the next teacher is waiting for them, as they claim. This scheduling will be helpful to them and it will be a more student-friendly mode of examinations. More so, when scheduling is properly observed, the conduct of classes during scheduled exam should also be avoided to free students from confusion and stress.

Some respondents also claim that corridors and vacant rooms should be kept from noise not to disturb students taking the test. In addition, the respondents indicated that format, content and payment of test papers be regulated.

The respondents also listed factors which were categorized as students' needs. Although these are not directly needed during examinations when these are addressed, they may lead to a better test performance. These are: more and updated books and classroom-based technology, and well-lighted and well-ventilated classrooms. Five respondents suggested that a student lounge be built for students to sit, take lunch or make projects and assignments to save time from traveling home and back to school for the next subject.

While others are claiming for a lesser extra-curricular activities and more classroom interaction, others claim for an opportunity for curricular academic competitions, and posted result of examinations as well as over-all academic performance. This claim may have been inspired by what they see in movies, on exam results posted in bulletin boards using their school ID numbers as personal identification. This allows students who did not perform well in the test to be free of embarrassment and/or bullying.

When these issues are addressed, and when these suggestions are considered, students may feel motivated and make a better engagement in class which would ultimately result in a successful performance in the LET.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The following are derived conclusions.

1. The respondents prepare themselves spiritually, physically and mentally for the examinations, however, unlike some students who are well supported in their schooling, others have lesser preparation for the test due to work and livelihood. Only a few practices some helpful techniques in taking the test, while some others are not careful with test directions and in analyzing test items. Most of the respondents are more mindful of their scores than looking for correct answers of items they did not get. Student engagement is not significant, which is a factor that ultimately affects performance of students in school and in the LET.

2. Teachers did not fail to make necessary class preparations before the examinations except those who failed to meet their classes religiously or who included items in the test or made a test with topics not discussed in class. When students are accustomed to this type of test environment, it may affect their test attitudes which may ultimately result in an unfavorable performance in the LET.

3. The respondents expect their teachers to closely monitor students during examinations to avoid cheating increasing student engagement to review. Further, the students need a noise-free exam area for a more focused concentration in the test. These behaviors they observed in the classroom may result in the formation of positive attitude towards taking examinations thereby improve their performance in the LET.

4. The respondents claim of a test protocol in its highest standards from the preparation to the culmination of examination schedule. This motivates them to increase their engagement

in their classes thereby increasing their academic performance, which may result in a favorable outcome in the LET.

The claims of the respondents may be some of the unidentified reasons why students do not perform well in the LET. This should be promptly addressed by all concerned stakeholders to scaffold the students' performance in the LET.

Recommendation

The following are the recommendations:

1. As a means of improving learning engagement, students must develop test-taking abilities such as seeking for the correct answer to test questions with incorrect marks right away and making this a habit. Once formed, this mindset may aid in achieving a good grade in the exams and on the LET.

2. Teachers must create test questions that follow the LET format so that students become familiar with the setup. In this instance, students may view their summative exams as a conditioning component and a concrete way of preparing for the LET. This may also develop the students' test-taking skills while studying to ensure better performance in the LET.

3. The administration must devise a systematized and student-friendly approach to exam timetable to keep students from becoming shattered during exams. In this way, students do not consider examinations as dreadful student activity but a gratifying way of learning engagement as they await a satisfying test result. If this positive test attitude is imbibed, it may help in the formation of emotional stability among students taking the LET and ultimately may result to a promising outcome.

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